

METHODS OF TEACHING HIGHER MATHEMATICS FOR NON-SPECIALIST STUDENTS IN A PRACTICAL ORIENTED WAY

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Annotation: This article analyzes the need, purpose and methodological foundations of teaching higher mathematics in a practice-oriented manner for students studying in non-specialized areas. The main focus is on increasing the practical importance of mathematics in students' professional activities, combining theoretical knowledge with real-life tasks. The article describes effective methods such as teaching practical problem solving, selecting problems adapted to professional activities, and using innovative teaching technologies.

Keywords: higher mathematics, non-specialized students, teaching methodology, pedagogical technologies, critical thinking, motivation.

Introduction

In the 21st century, the acceleration of digitization, innovation and technological progress in all spheres of society puts forward modern requirements for the higher education system. In particular, increasing the practical importance of higher mathematics for students studying in non-specialized areas has become an urgent issue. Because mathematics develops analytical thinking, forms the competencies of systematic thinking and solving complex problems. Therefore, there is an increasing need to prepare students to solve real-life problems by teaching mathematics not only on a theoretical basis, but also in a practice-oriented manner.

Since mathematical knowledge is often delivered in an abstract form in the traditional education system, interest and motivation in science are not sufficiently formed in non-specialist students. Practice-oriented teaching allows students to form mathematical skills necessary for their professional activities, integrate theoretical knowledge with practical issues, and develop independent thinking skills.

This article analyzes the methodological foundations, effective pedagogical approaches, and possibilities for using innovative technologies for teaching higher mathematics to non-specialist students in a practice-oriented manner. The main goal of the study is to increase the practical value of mathematics for students, ensure the application of learned theoretical knowledge in professional activities, and develop methods for effectively organizing the educational process.

The need for practice-oriented teaching of higher mathematics

For students in non-specialized areas, higher mathematics often plays an instrumental role. That is, mathematics serves as a tool for the formation of basic professional knowledge for these students, logical modeling of technical and economic processes, and the development of skills for analyzing data and drawing conclusions. Therefore, higher mathematics courses should be adapted to their professional needs, integrated with real-life tasks and problems in professional activity.

While in the traditional approach, higher mathematics is mainly based on theoretical concepts, formulas and proofs, the modern approach requires explaining topics based on practical tasks, acquiring knowledge through solving real-life problems. In this case, showing the importance of mathematics in students' professional activities increases motivation and indicates the practical value of knowledge.

Principles of practice-oriented teaching.

The following principles are followed in teaching higher mathematics to non-specialists with a focus on practice:

principle of professional relevance: the mathematical concepts and methods being studied should be directly related to the students' future professional activities.

principle of problem-based learning: students are presented with real or close-to-real practical problems to be solved and are encouraged to solve them independently or in groups.

principle of activity and independence: students do not just accept ready-made knowledge, but independently search, analyze and draw practical conclusions.

principle of innovative approach: the teaching process is diversified through the use of information and communication technologies, simulation programs, online platforms.

Main methods and forms of teaching

The following methods are widely used in teaching higher mathematics in a practice-oriented manner:

Problem-based learning method: During the lesson, more real-life mathematical situations are raised and their solutions are worked on than theoretical material.

Project-based learning method: Students are assigned projects such as mathematical modeling, statistical analysis, economic calculations and are required to complete them independently or in groups.

Case-study method: Students analyze a specific real situation (for example, optimal resource allocation in the production process) using mathematical models.

Interactive methods: Interactive learning is organized using online tests, virtual laboratories, mathematical visualization programs.

Differential approach: Educational materials are adapted, taking into account the specific characteristics of students' knowledge level and professional areas.

Criteria for selecting practical problems

The problems selected in practice-oriented training must meet the following criteria:

Relevance to professional activity: the content of the problem must be related to the student's future professional field (engineering, economics, technology, medicine, etc.).

Realism: the problem must be based on situations encountered in real life or approximated to it.

Logical complexity: the problem must force the student to independently analyze, think strategically, and approach creatively.

Possibility of mathematical modeling: the problem must allow the student to build mathematical models, create formulas, and algorithms.

For example, tasks are prepared on topics such as "optimization of product production for maximum profit" for students in the economic field, "calculation of material durability and load" for students in the technical field, and "mathematical model of virus spread" for students in the medical field.

Discussion

Higher mathematics has always been one of the main basic disciplines of the education system. However, for modern students, especially young people studying in non-specialized areas, mathematics is often perceived as a difficult and distant subject. In their opinion, this subject is rarely directly applied in solving real-life problems. In fact, mathematics is the main tool that forms a culture of thinking, teaches logical analysis and rational decision-making. Only if the methods and approaches to teaching it are adapted to the requirements of the time, students can feel this truth in their own experience.

Practice-oriented teaching shows students that mathematics is not only a set of formulas and abstract concepts, but also what a powerful tool it is in solving real-life problems. For example, for a student studying economics, knowing statistical analysis methods, methods of constructing or optimizing regression models are necessary skills not only for completing an educational task, but also for their future professional activities.

From this point of view, a significant change will occur in the role of the teacher. Now the teacher is not a ready-made provider of information, but a coach who guides the student's independent research and practical activities. The student, on the other hand, becomes not a passive listener, but an active participant and creator of knowledge. Through practical tasks, project work, case studies and group discussions, the essence and practical significance of mathematics are revealed on their own.

However, implementing this approach also presents some challenges. First, it is necessary to create a database of practical problems suitable for each professional area and to constantly update it. Second, teachers must have the skills to combine their knowledge not only with fundamental mathematics, but also with professional areas. Third, practice-oriented lessons require more time, resources and technical support.

Nevertheless, experience shows that practice-oriented education increases students' motivation, develops in them the skills of independent thinking, decision-making and critical analysis. Most importantly, students begin to perceive mathematics as a useful tool for their professional growth. For them, mathematics becomes not a dry theory, but a key to analyzing and understanding real life.

Therefore, in the conditions of modern education, the process of teaching higher mathematics to non-specialists must change: it should serve not only to know, but also to form competencies for doing, obtaining practical results and using them in their activities. Only then will mathematics strengthen its position as a truly applied science.

Conclusion

Teaching higher mathematics to non-specialists in a practice-oriented manner is one of the important requirements of today's educational process. The results of the study show that through a practice-based approach, students understand the real-life significance of the theoretical knowledge being studied and develop skills in the effective use of mathematical tools in their professional activities.

In practice-oriented teaching, it is necessary to be based on the principles of professional relevance, problem-based learning, independence and the use of innovative technologies. In this case, the educational process should be enriched with real-life issues, problems in professional activities and tasks organized on a project basis.

Also, the role of the teacher is not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a mentor who guides and encourages students' independent research activities. Ensuring the active participation of students, developing creative and critical thinking skills should become the main goal of the educational process.

In general, teaching higher mathematics with a focus on practice serves not only to increase the professional readiness of students, but also to develop their universal competencies such as independent thinking, analysis and decision-making. This creates a solid foundation for training qualified specialists who meet the requirements of the modern labor market.

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